
GENDER AND TRAINEE RECRUITMENT DECISIONS IN THE IGBO APPRENTICESHIP PRACTICE IN ENUGU METROPOLIS, ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: The study focused on gender and trainee recruitment decisions in the Igbo apprenticeship practice in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives sought to examine the extent of the relationship between gender and honest attitude of apprentices, and ascertain the relationship between gender and disposition to teamwork among apprentices in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. The study had a population of 1,945 entrepreneurs of the apprenticeship practice. A sample-size of 331 entrepreneurs for the apprenticeship practice was determined, through Taro Yamane's formula at 5% tolerance and 95% level of confidence. Instruments utilized for data collection were primarily structured questionnaire and interviews. A total of 331 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, while 324 copies were properly filled / returned, leaving 7 copies not properly filled. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Two hypotheses were formulated in line with research objectives and questions. Data collected were tested and analyzed, using Simple Linear Regression Statistical tool and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 5% level of significance. The findings indicated that there was a significant positive relationship between gender and honest attitude of apprentices ($r = .948, P < .05$), and there was also, a significant positive relationship between gender and disposition to teamwork among apprentices ($r = .931, p < .05$). The study concluded that the data collected and analyzed indicated a significant positive relationship between all gender and all trainee recruitment variables measured. Consequently, there was significant positive relationship between gender and trainee recruitment decisions in the Igbo apprenticeship practice. The study, therefore, recommended among other things that masters of apprenticeship practice are encouraged to investigate gender differences in skill perceptions, explore how male and female trainees perceive the significance of honest and teamwork skills in recruitment decisions. They are also encouraged not to consider cultural beliefs and gender norms in the Igbo communities with respect to female gender in recruitment decisions, rather be based on acquisition of necessary skills, availability and determination of the apprentices so as to promote gender equality and inclusivity in recruitment and selection processes.

INTRODUCTION

The Igbo Apprenticeship practice has been given different explanations by several schools of thoughts and scholars (Nzewi, Onwuka, & Onyesom, 2017). The practice involves more of an appealing to an individual or a

person that is determined to embark and learn a particular skill or job by working for a fixed period, for someone who is very good at that job or skill (Inyang, & Agwadu, 2017). The Apprentice can be a teenager or young person, male or female that embarks on learning or receiving practical training skills, and also occasionally theoretical knowledge in a specialized area of vocation, trade or occupation he/she has chosen to trade on for a period of time. And for apprenticeship, some have advised that it is an operative mechanism for easy learning shift for young people to move from school-based approach to the world of work or other tasks associated with such (Olulu, & Udeorah, 2018).

The system of apprenticeship in Igbo originates from patriarchal traditions that kept women out of economic activities and restricted their role to housework. Therefore, women were largely excluded from apprenticeship practice, which was seen as a man's domain. The primary purpose of apprenticeship system was to transfer skills, knowledge, and wealth from one generation to the next, which further contributed to the inequalities between men and women in terms of work and economic opportunity. However, due to social changes and increasing awareness of gender parity, the dynamics of apprenticeship system has changed. Today, women are questioning traditional norms and seeking economic opportunities outside of the home. They are motivated by reasons such as financial autonomy, family support and self-determining (Ogochukwu and Ignatius, 2024).

Although Igbo apprenticeships for women are still lower than apprenticeships for men, there are a number of promising women apprentices and entrepreneurs emerging. Women are starting to enter the trades that were traditionally male occupations, such as tailoring, hairstyling, catering, and fashion designing. These women apprentices face a lot of obstacles, including social stigma, limited resources, and insufficient support networks. However, their resilience and perseverance make them able to overcome these obstacles and find their niche within the apprenticeship system (Ogochukwu and Ignatius, 2024).

Gender bias is pervasive at work and in organizations, creating inequalities at every stage of employment cycle. Several factors compound across women's careers' producing, and sustaining gender inequality from recruitment to selection to promotion. Such factors include, cultural norms and gender roles, recruitment bias, structural barriers to career advancement, limited promotion opportunities, workplace environment and gendered socialization, economic factors etc. The Igbo apprentice system is a leeway of their entrepreneurial make-up, where a tactical training process is exploited to train mostly young men of Igbo stock into entrepreneurial ventures by established entrepreneurs locally known as Oga, (Ejo-Orusa, 2019). This venture can be a trade, an enterprise or a vocation in some cases, serving also as a house help. The Ogas are former apprentices that had served and were settled with seed capitals to begin their own enterprises (Alike & Umunze, 2019). This system is informal and has unstructured training practice to learn and master skills required to embark on own enterprise. Dishonest on the part of the Master or the apprentice has tended to dent the good intentions of the Nwa-boi apprenticeship system.

Statement of the Problem

The Igbo Apprenticeship has been around for over several decades, following traditional Igbo established norms and conventions, albeit unwritten. It has similar characteristics to the master apprenticeship relationship, where the apprentice is the teen learner, and the master is the experienced business-owner.

Igbo apprenticeships emerged because of low competences in many skills, including bad knowledge-based qualifications, lack of functional skills, and poor competence-based qualification of small and medium firms, all

of which are significant elements of our research in this paper. Igbo apprenticeships in Enugu State would suffer from a lack of invention and creativity, a lack of dedication to quality, a lack of most useful skills necessary for successful apprenticeships, such skills include, interpersonal skills, honest skills, teamwork skills, obedience / loyalty skills, etc. Thus, aggregating all these problems are what informed the researcher to embark on this study to proffer sustainable solutions to these potential problems.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study focused on gender and trainee recruitment decisions in the Igbo Apprenticeship practice in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the extent of the relationship between gender and honest attitude of apprentices.
- ii. Ascertain the relationship between gender and disposition to teamwork among apprentices.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Gender

Gender stereotype is a common belief about what psychological traits are characteristic of each sex (Eagly et al., 2000). The male stereotype is characterized by high amounts of “masculine” traits that are task-oriented or agentic (Eagly, *et al.*, 2000). Gender bias can manifest in various forms during the recruitment and selection process, leading to unequal opportunities for candidates. Job descriptions may unintentionally use language that is more appealing to one gender over the other, thereby discouraging potentially qualified candidates from applying.

Igbo Apprentice System

The Igbo apprentice system is a form of indentured apprenticeship where young individuals, known as trainee apprentice" are placed under the care and tutelage of a master or mistress, referred to as the “Oga” or “Madam”." The Oga or Madam could be a successful trader, artisan, or professional in a particular field.

Trainee Recruitment Decision

Trainee recruitment today is not what it used to be, a simple matter of selecting the most qualified young people from a pile of applications. Recruitment challenges are the results of the changing training market. The demographic shift and the trend towards more academic education have resulted in an ever-shrinking number of applicants in the vocational training system. Young people interested in vocational training are becoming a scarce commodity. And more and more frequently, the qualifications of applicants do not meet companies' training requirements.

Factors for Consideration in the Selection of Apprentices

Honest

Honest is the suitability of words and behavior, conformity of words to factual events, or conformity of actions with applicable regulations. These conformities become truth, truth in words and deeds, and are correct in carrying out rules. Honest as an aspiration and an obligation, emphasizing it in their mission statements, corporate philosophies, and business codes (Biodgett, Dumas, & Zanzi, 2011). However, honest can be costly. For example, honestly reporting low earnings can harm a company's valuation. A leader who honestly reports their failures might have a lower likelihood of retaining his leadership role. In difficult conversations, such as

those involving negative feedback or the delivery of bad news, honest may have social costs (Lavelle, Folger, & Manegold, 2016; Levine, Roberts & Cohen, 2020; Scott, 2019; Shell, 2021).

Teamwork

Team can be described as a group of people who work together to achieve the same goals and objectives for the good of the service users and organizations in order to deliver a good quality of service. Team work is the ability to work together towards a common vision. Teamwork is a fuel that allows common people to attain uncommon results. Collective action is widely recognized as a positive force for teamwork in any organization or institution to succeed. According to Wageman (2021) “company’s teamwork is the only way anything gets accomplished with quality and efficiency and a major reason why economic growth is under control and company’s success is scrutinized by top management to achieve the desired goals.

Conceptual Framework

Fig 2.1 Conceptual model of the study.

Source: Authorities that contributed to the Gender and Apprentices Traits of this study:

Theoretical Framework

Skill Acquisition Theory

This study was anchored on skill Acquisition Theory (SAT) propounded by Paul Fitts and Michael Posner (1967) and later expanded by John Anderson (1982), as well as K. Anders Ericson (1993) who contributed with the concept of deliberate practice, emphasizing the role of sustained, focused practice in skill mastery.

The skill Acquisition Theory posit that individuals learn and develop skills through stages, often beginning with conscious, deliberate practice and moving toward automatic, expert performance. The major assumptions of skill Acquisition theory are:

- i. Stage – Based progression: The skill Acquisition theory posits that skill acquisition follows a sequential process. New learners begin with basic, conscious engagement. (cognitive stage) develop through practice (associative stage) and eventually perform tasks almost automatically (autonomous stage).
- ii. Practice and repetition: Skill development requires consistent deliberate practice. Progression depends on time and quality of training, making access to structured learning environments (like apprenticeships) crucial.

Empirical Review

Chineze (2022) examined the effect of Igbo trade apprenticeship system on unemployment reduction in Onitsha. The specifics objectives were as follows: Ascertain the impact of apprentice skill acquisition on

unemployment reduction in Onitsha: The research anchored on the skill acquisition theory were adopted in this study. Primary sources of data were used and the instrument employed in collecting information from the population was through structured questionnaire. The research adopted sampling techniques were purposive sampling. From the analyses tested, the study found that: Apprentice skill acquisition has significant effect on unemployment reduction at Onitsha: Apprenticeship training system has significant effect on unemployment reduction at Onitsha:

Ezeajughu, (2021) examined the Igbo man perspectives of apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development in southeast Nigeria. This paper analytically investigates peculiar sources, circumstances and skills that are the fulcrum of increasing socio-economic performance of the Igbo people. The study finds that entrepreneurial performance of the Igbos is underscored by their economic culture and value, which are highly existential in their traditions and belief system.

Rosemary and Joy (2020) investigated honest in business as a panacea for achieving business sustainability among SMEs in Port-Harcourt. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The population for the study was 1,200 registered SMEs in Port-Harcourt. A sample size of 183 male and female owners of SMEs was randomly selected for the study using simple random sampling technique. The study identified characteristics of honest in business to include being straightforward, having a strong moral principle, being able to gain the trust of others among others. The study also identified increase in customer patronage, growth and development of business, increase in profit, favourable public business image and increase in market share as benefits of honest in business. High risk of failure, low patronage, creating opportunity for higher competition and reduction in profit and market turnover were also identified as consequences of dishonest in business.

Sonal and Theophilus (2020) assessed the impact of teamwork on organizational productivity on the staff members of Kwashieman Anglican Basic School of the Accra Metropolitan Assembly, Omanjor M/A Basic School under the Ga-West Assembly and Ablekuma Anglican Basic School in the Ga-Central Assembly of the Greater Accra Region. The study utilized quantitative techniques to analyze the relationship between the variables that is Teamwork, Esprit de corps (Team Spirit), team trust, recognition and rewards and organizational productivity. The study shows that there is a significant positive impact of the predictors on the response variable with an adjusted R² of 70.5%. the study recommends that teamwork activities have to be adopted in order to enhance organizational Productivity.

METHODOLOGY

Given the nature of this study, Survey research design was adopted. A survey is a series of self-report measures administered either through an interview or a written questionnaire (Stangor, 2007). It is a well-accepted practice for collecting data in many fields of research, particularly in the Social Sciences and Organizational Behaviour (Roztock and Morgan, 2002). The population for this study was 1,945 entrepreneurs, who have adopted the apprenticeship practice for more than 10 years in the small and medium-scale enterprises in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria. Sample size was 331 entrepreneurs of the apprenticeship practice derived through Taro Yamane's formula. The sampling techniques utilized describe how the participants were selected and how data were collected. In this study, the entrepreneurs who have adopted the apprenticeship practice for more than 10 years in SMEs in Enugu metropolis Enugu State, Nigeria, were used as target population. In this

study, copies of structured questionnaire were distributed to elicit responses from the respondents. In this study, the descriptive statistics such as frequency counts with simple percentages were used to analyze the research questions. At the inferential level of analyses, hypotheses I and II were tested, using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 5% level of significance to determine the extent of correlation between the dependent and independent variables. All the analyses were done through the application of statistical package for Social Science (SPSS version 25.00 windows).

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho: There is no positive relationship between gender and honest attitude of apprentices.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std Deviation	N
Gender	1.6156	.85596	324
Honest Attitude	1.6031	.79299	324

Table 4.7: Correlations

Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	.948**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	324	324
Honest Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.949**	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	324	324

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table shows the descriptive statistics of the gender and honest 'attitude with, a mean response of 1.6156 and std. deviation of .85596 for gender and a mean response of 1.6031 and std. deviation of .79299 for honest attitude and number of respondents (324). By careful observation of standard deviation values, there is not much difference in terms of the standard⁵ deviation scores. This implies that there is about the same variability of data points between the dependent and independent variables.

Table shows that the pearson correlation coefficient for gender and honest attitude. The correlation coefficient shows 0.948. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2tailed) and implies that there is a significant positive relationship between gender and honest attitude ($r = .948$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 322 degrees of freedom ($df. = n-2$) at. alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .948. p < .05$),

However, since the computed $r = .948$, is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. We therefore conclude that there is a positive relationship between gender and honest of attitude of apprentice ($r = .948, P < .05$)

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho: There is no positive relationship between gender and disposition to teamwork among apprentices.

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std Deviation	N
Gender	1.7000	.84021	324

Disposition to teamwork	1.7063	.77255	324
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Table 4.9: Correlations

Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	.931 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	324	324
Disposition to teamwork	Pearson Correlation	.932 ^{**}	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	324	324

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table shows the descriptive statistics of the gender and disposition to teamwork with a mean response of 1.7000 and std. deviation of .84021 for gender and a mean response of 1.7063* and std. deviation of .77255 for disposition to teamwork and number of respondents (324). By careful observation of standard deviation values, there is not much difference in terms of the standard deviation scores. This implies that there is about the same variability of data points between the dependent and independent variables.

Table shows that Pearson correlation coefficient for gender and disposition to teamwork. The correlation coefficient shows 0.931. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed) and implies that there is a significant positive relationship between gender and disposition to teamwork ($r = .931$). The computed correlation coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .195$ with 318 degrees of freedom ($df = n - 2$) at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .931, p < .05$). However, since the computed $r = .931$ is greater than the table value of $.195$, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. We therefore, conclude that there is a positive relationship between gender and disposition to teamwork ($r = .931, P < .05$).

Summary of Findings

The findings at the end of this study include the following

- i. There is a significant positive relationship between gender and honest attitude of apprentice ($r = .948, P < .05$).
- ii. There is a significant positive relationship between gender and disposition to teamwork among apprentices ($r = .931, P < .05$).

Conclusion

The Igbo apprenticeship practice has been a longstanding business incubation or entrepreneurship practice in the South-East geo-political zone of Nigeria, which had played a significant role in the economic growth and development of the zone. The study evaluated the influence of gender in selecting new apprentices for working and learning in the apprenticeship practice. Data collected and analyzed indicate that there is significant positive relationship between all gender and all trainee recruitment variables measured. Consequently, we conclude that there is a significant positive relationship between gender and trainee recruitment decisions in the Igbo apprenticeship practice in Enugu Metropolis, Enugu State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study therefore recommended among other things that masters (entrepreneurs) of the apprenticeship practice are encouraged to investigate gender differences in skill perception and explore how male and female trainees perceive the significance of honest and teamwork skills in recruitment decisions. Also masters of the apprenticeship practice are equally encouraged not to consider the influence of gender norms and cultural beliefs prevailing in Igbo Communities, regarding gender in recruitment decisions of apprentices, but be based on acquisition of necessary skills, availability and determination of the apprentices, so as to promote gender equality and inclusivity in recruitment and selection processes.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study can contribute to knowledge in several ways leveraging on applicable models of study such as: understanding Gender dynamics in Apprenticeship practices. The study can contribute to knowledge by providing insights into how gender influences recruitment decisions within traditional apprenticeship practices. It can also highlight barriers that may exist for female apprentices and identify biases in the criteria for selection. Gender role theory is one of the models of study, upon which this study contributes to knowledge. The model can be employed to analyze how societal norms and expectations, with respect to gender roles influence the recruitment process. It also helps in understanding the underlying assumptions that affect decisions and can reveal disparities in opportunities available to male and female apprentices.

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